

Operando visualization of Li distribution in solid-state batteries using focused ion beam-secondary ion mass spectrometry imaging

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Operando analysis
Correlative microscopy
SEM/SIMS
Li-ion transport
Solid-state batteries

ABSTRACT

A thorough understanding of lithium transport pathways through electrode/electrolyte during battery operation is crucial for developing high-performance all-solid-state batteries (SSBs). However, limitations in existing characterization techniques make real-time tracking of lithium transport challenging. In this article, we report on the development of a setup for *operando* secondary electron (SE) and secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) imaging of SSBs. We designed a specialized electrochemical cycling setup and a sample holder, enabling simultaneous battery operation and SE-SIMS imaging inside a prototype platform that combines a dual-beam focused ion beam-scanning electron microscope (FIB-SEM) with a double-focusing magnetic sector SIMS system (referred hereafter as FIB-SEM-SIMS). The developed setup allows battery cycling using a commercial potentiostat while maintaining the necessary sample bias for simultaneous SIMS imaging. To demonstrate the capabilities of this setup, we imaged lithium-ion transport in a solid-state Li-half cell with a ⁶Li rich foil working electrode. A chronopotentiometry (CP) sequence was applied to the half-cell within the FIB-SEM-SIMS instrument. SIMS analysis at various stages of the CP sequence captured changes in ⁶Li content in the electrolyte, resulting from ⁶Li ion migration from the working electrode due to the applied current. The methodology described here enables real-time visualization of transient changes in the spatial distribution of Li during battery operation, making it highly valuable for detailed investigations of ion transport pathways in SSBs. We also discuss strategies to minimize probable measurement artifacts arising from use of charged ion and electron beams for *operando* analysis.

1. Introduction

Solid-state Li-ion batteries have attracted considerable attention as the next frontier in energy storage systems due to their higher energy density, stability, and safety compared to conventional Li-ion batteries with liquid electrolytes [1–3]. However, for their successful commercialization and widespread adoption, it is essential to gain a detailed understanding of the structural and chemical degradation processes that occur within these batteries during operation. Pre- and post-mortem (*ex-situ*) analysis of battery components fall short in this regard, as they cannot directly correlate the degradation mechanisms with the electrochemical performance of the batteries. Furthermore, the disassembly of batteries for *ex-situ* analysis can lead to additional microstructural alterations and contamination due to exposure to air or other

contaminants during the transfer of components for analysis. Thus, development of methods which allow analysis of batteries in their operational environment (*in-situ*) and during their operation (*operando*) are crucial for overcoming these challenges [4,5].

In recent years several *operando* workflows have been designed for studying the intricate mechanisms occurring inside lithium batteries. Among them, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) techniques can offer excellent spatial resolution for observing microstructural alterations. *Operando* electron microscopy has been widely employed to study morphological degradation phenomena, such as the growth of Li dendrites and the formation of "dead" lithium [6–9]. However, the conventional chemical analysis techniques associated with them such as energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) or electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) are often not

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sufficient for direct detection of Li [10], the key component of these batteries. This limitation arises because the characteristic transition energy of Li is around 55 eV, which is too low to be captured by conventional EDX detectors. Furthermore, EDX cannot detect trace elements [11]. On the other hand, although EELS is capable of detecting Li, it also has a limited detection range like EDX and requires thin samples for accurate analysis. Otherwise, the plasmon peaks of thick sample may mask the Li-K edge [12], complicating Li detection. Other imaging techniques, such as neutron imaging and atom probe tomography (APT), have been used for imaging Li, but each has its own constraints. Neutron imaging is limited in terms of spatial resolution, while APT requires complex sample preparation and is restricted to analyzing very small volumes. As a result, high-sensitivity methods for the direct detection and nanoscale imaging of Li remain scarce.

In this context, secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) is a very promising alternative as it can analyze low-Z elements such as H [13] or Li [14,15] even at trace concentrations (down to ppm level concentration). SIMS can even distinguish between different isotopes of an element [13,16], which provides an opportunity for detailed analysis of Li transport in batteries using isotopically labelled electrodes or electrolytes.

Many studies have already utilized SIMS for *ex-situ* chemical analysis of lithium batteries [14,15,17,18]. While post-mortem SIMS imaging of lithium battery components described in these publications provides partial insights into the degradation mechanisms, capturing a dynamic evolution of lithium distribution at high spatial resolution during battery operation is crucial for a comprehensive understanding of local interfacial processes, charge transport dynamics, and degradation mechanisms.

A few recent studies have applied SIMS analysis to solid-state batteries in operational environment [19,20], primarily investigating the lithium content variations in composite electrodes during charge-discharge cycles. More recently, correlative secondary electron (SE) and SIMS imaging of solid-state Li batteries before and after electrochemical cycling, with nanometer-scale spatial resolution, has also been demonstrated [21]. However, one major limitation of these reported quasi-*operando* SIMS approaches is that the electrochemical processes of the battery are paused or stopped during SIMS analysis. This interruption causes the battery to move towards a state of electrochemical equilibrium during analysis, which does not reflect the inherently non-equilibrium nature of battery operation. Therefore, to gain thorough understanding of the ion transport and battery degradation mechanisms, a more advanced approach is needed that allows for simultaneous SIMS analysis while the battery is in operation.

In this work, we present a novel *operando* methodology for SIMS imaging of solid-state Li-ion batteries, enabling real-time analysis without interrupting the electrochemical process. Our approach uses a specially designed electrochemical cycling unit and a sample holder, along with a prototype platform that combines a dual-beam FIB-SEM instrument with a compact double-focusing magnetic sector SIMS system [22] (FIB-SEM-SIMS). This advanced FIB-SEM-SIMS instrument offers high-resolution chemical imaging with detection limits down to the ppm level, while also capturing detailed topographic and microstructural information from the same zone via SE imaging (ion or electron induced). Furthermore, unlike the Time of Flight (ToF)-SIMS instruments, no pulsing of primary or secondary ion beam is required for the magnetic sector SIMS systems. Hence, no duty cycle is present, and the system is operated in continuous primary beam irradiation and secondary beam extraction mode. This results in significantly faster data acquisition compared with the ToF-SIMS setups and for considerably higher signal levels. As a proof-of-concept of our methodology, we visualized the dynamic spatial redistribution of lithium ions in a battery sample during a chronopotentiometry (CP) sequence in a solid-state Li-half cell. The working electrode (W.E.) was a foil enriched in the ^6Li isotope, while the electrolyte and the counter electrode (C.E.) both had natural lithium abundance (i.e., the isotopic ratio is $^6\text{Li}\sim 7.6\%$ and

$^7\text{Li}\sim 92.4\%$). This allowed us to differentiate between the Li ions migrating from the W.E. during battery operation and the Li ions already present in the electrolyte before the charging started. We believe that the methodology presented here can be instrumental in understanding fundamental processes inside Li-ion batteries such as ion transport through passivation layers formed at battery interface and charge transport properties of the different phases of composite electrode or electrolyte materials.

2. Materials and methods

The electrolyte used for the proof-of-concept study described here is a gel polymer electrolyte (referred hereafter as GPE) based on poly(vinylidene fluoride -co- hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF) as polymer matrix plasticized with a solution of polyethylene glycol dimethyl ether (PEGDME, $M_n = 500$ g/mol) as solvent and lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide (LiTFSI) as lithium salt with a solvent ethylene oxide units to lithium cation (EO/Li) ratio of 20/1. Details regarding the preparation of the GPE and its performance can be found elsewhere [23]. The W.E. of the symmetrical Li metal cell was a lithium foil prepared by laminating ^6Li -chunks (enriched to 95.4 % in ^6Li , immersed in mineral oil) purchased from Sigma Aldrich (CAS- No. 14, 258-72-1). The counter electrode was a Li foil having natural isotopic abundance (delivered by Alfa Aesar, CAS-No. 7439-93-2).

2.1. Design of *operando* analysis setup

The main challenge in using the FIB-SEM-SIMS setup described above for *operando* imaging is that a strong electric field is required between the sample and the SIMS system for efficiently extracting the secondary ions generated during the sputtering process. For the FIB-SEM-SIMS instrument used in our study, this is done by keeping the sample at ± 500 V (depending on whether positive or negative secondary ions are being analyzed) with respect to the grounded first electrode of the SIMS extraction optics, which is at 0.5 mm distance from the sample surface during analysis [22]. As the sample is kept at 500 V, it is not possible to use any conventional potentiostat for performing any electrochemical experiments during SIMS analysis. Therefore, we chose to reference the electrodes of the potentiostat at 500 V. To implement this solution, we developed a customized high voltage electrochemical cycling setup that allows to reference the electrodes of a potentiostat (BioLogic SP150) at ± 500 V. This setup essentially disconnects the potentiostat from the earth ground, then the terminals of the potentiostat are put at 500 V by connecting an external 500 V DC power supply to the ground pin of the potentiostat cable. A schematic of this *operando* setup and the in-chamber view during analysis are presented in Fig. 1a and b. The working principle of this high voltage electrochemical cycling unit is described in detail in the supplementary section 1.1. A customized sample holder was used for electrochemical charging of the half-cell inside the FIB-SEM-SIMS platform (Fig. 1c). This holder is a modified version of the holder previously reported in the *in-situ* SIMS imaging study of Li dendrite growth in LLZO solid electrolyte [21]. The modification allows stable electrical connection during the *operando* analysis and enhanced electrochemical performance. To validate the functionality of the potentiostat when referenced at 500 V, electrochemical experiments were performed using both commercial coin cells and calibration cells provided by the potentiostat manufacturers. The objective was to determine whether potentiostat measurements with the terminals referenced at 500 V were consistent with those obtained under normal operating conditions (i.e., when referenced to earth ground). The results (see Supplementary Section 1.1) confirmed that referencing the potentiostat to 500 V did not cause any significant deviations in electrochemical performance compared to conventional battery cyclers. This validates the applicability of the developed setup for *operando* analysis.

Fig. 1. a) Schematic of the operando setup (ΔV denotes the small potential difference created between the potentiostat probes during the operando experiments, with 500 V set as the reference voltage). (b) In-chamber view during operando analysis. (c) 3D model of the sample holder. The parts in different color highlight the two electrical contacts of the holder that are separated from each other by an insulator. The battery sample is placed between these electrical contacts during operando analysis. The cross-sectional view shows the springs which apply the stacking pressure to the sample through the movable electrical contact (represented in Magenta).

2.2. Sample preparation for operando analysis

One major requirement of SIMS analysis is the planar surface of the samples. Topographical artifacts in sample surface can introduce (i) localized variations in the extraction field between the sample and the

SIMS system and (ii) changes in the angle of incidence of the primary ion beam. These effects cause fluctuations in the secondary ion (SI) signal, potentially leading to misinterpretation of SIMS data. To minimize these measurement artifacts, a semi-circular cell design was adopted in this proof-of-concept study, as analyzing the flat side of the cell reduces

Fig. 2. Schematic of the planar side of the half-cell used in the operando imaging proof-of-concept study. During the experiment, a chronopotentiometry (CP) sequence was applied by introducing a constant positive current (current density = $100 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$) to the ^6Li -enriched working electrode (W.E.), driving ^6Li ions inward into the electrolyte. SIMS imaging was performed at selected time points throughout the CP sequence, targeting areas of the electrolyte near the interface with the working electrode. This allowed visualization of the change in distribution of ^6Li ions within the electrolyte due to the applied current.

errors compared to the curved surface of a conventional circular coin cell. Firstly, an 8 mm diameter semicircular disc was prepared from the GPE using a lithium disc punching tool and a scalpel. For the isotopically labeled W.E., ${}^6\text{Li}$ metal chunks were washed with cyclohexane to remove residual mineral oil and then roll-pressed into foils approximately 0.4 mm thick. Then a 6 mm diameter circular piece was then punched from one of these foils using a lithium disc punching tool and cut into semicircular shape by a scalpel. The counter electrode was prepared similarly from a lithium foil with natural isotopic abundance. The GPE was then positioned between these two semicircular Li foils and carefully placed into the sample holder, with the flat side of the assembly oriented toward the electron/ion beam for analysis. Stacking pressure was applied using the movable compression plate of the sample holder to ensure good interfacial contact. A schematic representation of the cell assembly and *operando* experiment is provided in Fig. 2. All preparation and assembly steps were conducted inside an argon-filled glovebox ($\text{O}_2 < 1 \text{ ppm}$, $\text{H}_2\text{O} < 1 \text{ ppm}$) to prevent exposure to air and moisture. The assembled sample holder was then transferred to the FIB-SEM-SIMS instrument using an air-tight transfer shuttle to avoid contamination. Finally, the sample was introduced into the instrument chamber through an airlock attached to the FIB-SEM-SIMS system.

2.3. *Operando* experiment

The *operando* analysis was performed inside the FIB-SEM-SIMS platform as mentioned before. This platform consists of a dual beam FIB-SEM instrument (Scios DualBeam, Thermo Fisher Scientific) coupled to an in-house developed magnetic sector SIMS system. The dual beam instrument is equipped with a gallium (Ga) liquid metal ion source FIB-column installed at 52° with respect to the vertical electron beam column. The ${}^{69}\text{Ga}^+$ ions from the FIB are used as the primary ion beam for SIMS analysis in this setup. The SIMS system incorporates a continuous focal plane detector [24] enabling simultaneous detection of all secondary ion signals in the selected mass range. For the study reported here, the SIMS measurements were carried out with a primary ion beam energy of 30 keV and a probe current between 50 pA–70 pA. The two-dimensional elemental intensity maps were recorded with a resolution of 512×512 pixels, and a dwell time of 500 μs per pixel. The images were taken at field of view between 40 and 60 μm . For SIMS analysis, the battery samples used here were biased at +500 V using our electrochemical cycling setup (allowing positive secondary ions to be detected), which resulted in a primary beam impact energy of 29.5 keV. SE emitted due to interaction between the primary ion beam and the sample were also collected by the Everhart-Thornley (ET) detector (without sample bias) to analyze the microstructure of the electrolyte during the *operando* experiment.

After transferring the sample to the FIB-SEM-SIMS instrument from the glovebox, firstly SE images of the electrolyte in pristine state were taken by the electron beam. The primary electron beam energy was 5 keV and beam current was between 50 pA and 100 pA. After that, the sample stage was tilted at 52° to align the sample surface perpendicularly to the direction of the ion beam. Before starting any electrochemical experiments, SIMS images of the GPE were taken from regions near the interface between the GPE and the W.E. to understand the ${}^6\text{Li}$ distribution in the GPE in its pristine condition. Afterwards, the CP sequence was performed by applying a constant current density of 100 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$. The current density was calculated based on the contact area between the electrode and the GPE. The CP sequence was applied for 200 min, forcing mostly migration of ${}^6\text{Li}^+$ ions into the GPE. Considering the density of Li is 0.534 g/cm^3 and the contact area between the electrodes and the GPE is 0.141 cm^2 , it is estimated theoretically that the CP sequence would have resulted in consumption of 1.6 μm of the ${}^6\text{Li}$ rich foil. The voltage response of the cell was recorded during this period and SE as well as SIMS imaging was performed in the GPE near its interface with the W.E. at various time points of the electrochemical cycling. Data analysis was performed using Python and the software Fiji

[25]. ${}^6\text{Li}/({}^6\text{Li}+{}^7\text{Li})$ ratio maps were generated using Python by dividing the ${}^6\text{Li}$ counts of each pixel by the total intensity of both lithium isotopes for that pixel. Since both lithium isotopes have equivalent ionization yields and detection efficiencies for a given matrix [26], the 2D ratio maps provide a semi-quantitative measure of ionic transport relative to the pristine state of the analyzed sample.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. *Operando* analysis

Fig. 3(a) and (b) present SE images of the cell assembly and the morphology of the GPE surface, respectively, captured prior to any electrochemical experiments. The SE image in Fig. 3(b) reveals that the planar side of GPE exhibited some local surface topography. As explained before, such features in the imaged surface can introduce challenges in SIMS analysis. To mitigate these errors, relatively smoother regions of the GPE were selected for analysis. Nevertheless, some minor variation in SI signal due to surface topography remains visible in the SIMS images.

Fig. 4(a) shows the voltage profile recorded during the CP sequence. The red circles in the voltage profile denote the time points during which SIMS imaging was done. Fig. 4(b) shows the ${}^6\text{Li}/({}^6\text{Li}+{}^7\text{Li})$ ratio maps from one region of the GPE near its interface with W.E. during CP sequence. The 2D ratio maps in Fig. 4(b) clearly reveal a distinct increase in ${}^6\text{Li}$ fraction in that region as charging progressed. Fig. 5 shows a plot of the mean ${}^6\text{Li}$ fraction calculated from these images as a function of the time of electrochemical charging. From Figs. 4(b) and 5, it is evident that the ${}^6\text{Li}$ content in the electrolyte increased as the *operando* experiment progressed. This increase can be attributed to migration of ${}^6\text{Li}$ ions from the W.E. to the GPE during the CP sequence. The GPE was prepared by non-labelled LiTFSI salt, hence the ${}^7\text{Li}$ concentration in the GPE was significantly higher compared to ${}^6\text{Li}$. During the *operando* experiment, a portion of these ${}^7\text{Li}$ initially present in the GPE were plated on the C.E. and were replaced in the electrolyte by the ${}^6\text{Li}$ ions from the W.E., resulting in an increase in ${}^6\text{Li}$ fraction in the GPE as charging progresses.

These results validate the applicability of our setup for localized high-resolution visualization of the transient changes in lithium-ion distribution inside a battery during operation. To ensure the reproducibility and reliability of the results shown here, multiple regions were imaged during the *operando* experiment. The results from other regions (see Supplementary Information section 1.3) show a similar trend of increase in ${}^6\text{Li}$ content during electrochemical charging.

3.2. Spontaneous diffusion of Li ions and ion beam effect

Another notable observation from the results in Figs. 4b and 5 is that the ${}^6\text{Li}$ fraction in the electrolyte, measured before the start of electrochemical charging, is higher than the natural abundance of ${}^6\text{Li}$. The sample was left overnight in the FIB-SEM-SIMS instrument before measurements began, this allowed for spontaneous diffusion of ${}^6\text{Li}$ ions into the electrolyte due to the chemical concentration gradient between the electrode and the electrolyte, resulting in the measured higher ${}^6\text{Li}$ fraction even in absence of any electrical current. Several studies have documented the spontaneous diffusion (in the absence of an applied current) of lithium ions in liquid [27] and solid electrolytes [28–30]. Since this spontaneous diffusion phenomena occurs alongside ionic migration due to applied current during the charging experiment, it is crucial to determine how much of the observed increase in ${}^6\text{Li}$ fraction during the *operando* experiment is driven by the applied current compared to the contribution of the spontaneous diffusion of Li ions.

Additionally, during SIMS imaging, the ${}^{69}\text{Ga}^+$ primary ion beam generates a high positive charge density per pixel. Given the high mobility of Li ions, it is also essential to assess whether the primary ion beam causes any significant ionic redistribution within the GPE during

Fig. 3. (a) SE image of the W.E. | GPE | C.E. assembly. (b) Magnified SE image of the GPE surface. The SE image in (b) shows significant surface topography, which may cause variations in the SI signal during operando SIMS imaging. To replicate realistic battery operating conditions, no additional pre-processing of the electrolyte surface (e.g., ion beam milling for smoothing) was performed, as that could introduce contamination.

Fig. 4. (a) Voltage profile recorded during the operando experiment. A constant current of current density $100 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ was applied. The red circles are representative of the time points at which operando imaging was done. (b) Time series of 2D ${}^6\text{Li}/({}^6\text{Li} + {}^7\text{Li})$ ratio maps from the same ROI before and during electrochemical charging (Field of View (FOV) = $59 \mu\text{m} \times 59 \mu\text{m}$, 512×512 pixels, Primary beam energy = 30 keV, primary beam current = 50 pA, dwell time per pixel = 0.5 ms). The colour bar represents different values of ${}^6\text{Li}$ fraction. The top side of each SIMS ratio map corresponds to the region near the W.E., and the arrow indicates the direction of the incoming ${}^6\text{Li}$ ionic flux.

Fig. 5. Plot of variation of mean value of ⁶Li fraction in the ROI in Fig. 4.b as a function of the electrochemical charging time. The uncertainty for each measurement is represented by the standard error of mean for each ⁶Li/(⁶Li+⁷Li) ratio map.

the repeated SIMS imaging of the same region over time.

To address both of these issues, a separate reference experiment was conducted. Another Li-half cell similar to the one used in the *operando* experiment was prepared and placed inside the FIB-SEM-SIMS chamber, but no external electrical current was applied to it. This time, SIMS imaging was started immediately after placing the cell inside the instrument to evaluate the extent of ionic movement due to spontaneous diffusion and the potential impact of the primary ion beam. The imaging conditions and time intervals for imaging were kept identical to those used in the *operando* experiments.

Fig. 6 presents a representative dataset from these reference experiments, showing no significant increase in the ⁶Li fraction over time (The slight variation of intensity in the ratio maps here is primarily due to variation in SI signal due to sample topography). Datasets from multiple regions indicate that spontaneous diffusion at room temperature is negligible over the timeframe of the CP sequence. A significant increase in ⁶Li concentration due to spontaneous diffusion would only occur over much longer time intervals. These results are in agreement with previously reported studies [28]. Furthermore, the results in Fig. 6 also

Fig. 6. (a) ⁶Li/(⁶Li+⁷Li) ratio maps and (b) plot of the mean ⁶Li fraction as a function of time to understand spontaneous diffusion and primary ion beam effect on Li-redistribution. No external electrical current was applied during these measurements. The FOV for SIMS imaging was 52 μm, with all other imaging parameters being the same as those in Fig. 4. The images were acquired from the electrolyte near its interface with the W.E. The top side of each SIMS ratio map corresponds to the region near the W.E.

suggest that the positively charged primary ion beam does not cause any significant isotopic redistribution in the sample. Based on these findings, we can infer that the observed increase of ⁶Li fraction in the *operando* experiments (Fig. 4) is primarily due to the external current applied to the half-cell during the CP sequence.

3.3. Limitations

The findings presented in this study should be interpreted with caution, as they are based on analysis of limited number of regions in the sample. Additionally, since SIMS is a surface analysis technique, the observed variations in ⁶Li content on the sample surface cannot be directly correlated with ⁶Li migration in the bulk of the sample without further investigations by correlating the SIMS analysis with other 3D-imaging techniques [18]. Beam-induced artifacts may also impact the electrochemical performance of the cell. To evaluate the effect of the electron/ion beam on cell electrochemistry, we monitored changes in the open circuit voltage (OCV) in the presence of the probing beam. The beam currents used for SE-SIMS imaging did not cause any significant variations in the OCV compared to its value in the absence of the beam (see Supplementary Information, Section 1.4). Furthermore, no substantial deviations in the voltage profile were observed during SE-SIMS imaging when compared to the state with the beam turned off. But more rigorous investigation is needed for detailed understanding of the impact of charged primary ion/electron beam on electrochemistry of the cell during *operando* analysis.

From the *operando* imaging data for different regions, it was seen that the ⁶Li enrichment in the GPE occurred heterogeneously during electrochemical charging (see Supplementary Information, Section 1.3). Some regions had relatively higher ⁶Li concentration than others. The localized electric field gradients between the electrodes due to uneven plating/stripping and non-uniform contact between electrode and electrolyte can result in this observed heterogeneity. This could also be related to the ionic transport pathways in the GPE [23]. Detailed knowledge about the charge-transport pathways would require more extensive study by sampling more regions during analysis. However, that remains the subject of ongoing research, while this study focuses primarily on establishing a proof of concept for the *operando* workflow described here.

4. Conclusions

This work demonstrates a novel *operando* FIB-SIMS imaging

methodology that overcomes the limitations of existing SIMS based *in-situ/operando* imaging techniques by enabling simultaneous SIMS imaging and battery operation. Additionally, the use of a magnetic sector mass analyzer enables faster data acquisition compared to previously reported ToF-SIMS methods. While *operando* SEM techniques already exist, to the best of our knowledge, our setup is the first to facilitate fully *operando* correlative SE-SIMS imaging of solid-state batteries in the same instrument.

In the study presented here, we successfully tracked redistribution of Li ions within the solid electrolyte during electrochemical charging using isotope tracing. This highlights the potential of this technique for gaining detailed insights into Li transport mechanisms across the different phases of the composite electrodes and electrolytes which are now emerging as promising materials for SSBs. While this study focuses on Li half-cells, the methodology can also be adapted to investigate degradation mechanisms in solid-state batteries with different chemical properties. Potential applications include studying dendrite growth as a function of applied current and battery operation time as well as the formation and evolution of passivation layers in a running battery, and its impact on ionic transport.

Financial support

This work was funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101104032 (OPINCHARGE). We acknowledge Battery2030+ for their support of OPINCHARGE.

Data availability

The raw data used for the experimental results is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15704537>.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sayantan Sharma: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alexander Santiago:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology. **Maria Martinez-Ibañez:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology. **Mathieu Gerard:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Athira Suresh Kumar:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Olivier De Castro:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Tom Wirtz:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Santhana Eswara:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Omar Ramirez Sanchez and Olivier Bouton for the technical support and suggestions for developing the *operando* analysis setup.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2025.146728](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2025.146728).

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